

Navigating Cybersecurity Challenges in Healthcare: Challenges, Innovations, and EU Legal Framework for Connected Medical Devices

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Abstract. As healthcare technologies advance, their increasing interconnectivity and integration into more extensive IT networks and systems offer numerous advantages, such as real-time remote monitoring, early prevention and cost reduction. However, this heightened interconnectedness also presents significant challenges, with cyberattacks targeting medical devices and hospital networks emerging as prominent issues. Understandably, the cybersecurity of connected medical devices has gained paramount importance and urgency.

This paper outlines the principal cybersecurity challenges confronting the healthcare sector and introduces insights from the EU-funded CYLCOMED project, which aims to provide the latest technological solutions to address these challenges. Mainly, the paper seeks to identify the primary challenges encountered by the healthcare sector concerning cyber threats. Subsequently, it outlines the high-level architecture of the EU-funded CYLCOMED project (Cyber security toolbox for COnnected MEDical Devices) and its principal objectives, which aim to enhance the cybersecurity of connected, in vitro diagnostic, and software as medical devices (CMDs, IVDs, SaMD). Lastly, it provides a brief overview of the applicable EU legal framework governing the cybersecurity of medical devices.

Keywords: healthcare, cybersecurity, connected medical devices, legal challenges

1 Introduction

The scale and scope of digital transformation in the past decade have been remarkable, leading to significant advancements in everyday life. Previously confined to the domain of science fiction, technologies such as autonomous vehicles, artificial intelligence (AI), surgical robotics, the Internet of Things (IoT), and nanotechnology have become

a tangible and integral part of our everyday reality. However, these technological strides, often denoted as part of the fourth industrial revolution (Schwab, 2017), have brought about substantial societal challenges, with cybersecurity emerging as one of the most pressing concerns.

The World Economic Forum Global Risks Report (2024) identifies cyberattacks as a substantial global risk. With the increasing reliance on technology in our daily lives, the potential impact and severity of cyber-attacks are growing rapidly. Unsurprisingly, cybersecurity has gained significant traction across the public domain, becoming a top priority on political agendas globally (The White House, 2023; Ursula von der Leyen, 2021).

In the current cybersecurity landscape, healthcare is one of the most targeted sectors concerning cybersecurity incidents. The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) Report on the health threat landscape (2023a) reveals that the health sector is the third most targeted sector regarding the number of incidents. According to ENISA, patient data, including electronic health records, were ranked as the most targeted assets between January 2021 and March 2023. In addition to the ENISA report, a recent FBI Internet Crime Report (2023) has found that healthcare and public health were the most targeted critical infrastructure sectors in the US in 2023, with 249 officially reported attacks. Successful cyberattacks in healthcare may impede hospital operations, lead to the loss of sensitive patients' data, compromise patient safety, and, in extreme cases, lead to loss of life.

Despite a surge of interest and policy efforts to address cybersecurity challenges, the health sector still lags behind in terms of preparedness and maturity compared to other sectors, such as industrial and financial, to mention just a few.

This article does not seek to provide a comprehensive overview of the complex healthcare cybersecurity landscape. Rather, it concentrates on the foundational background of the proposed CYLCOMED cybersecurity solution. Accordingly, the focus is on something other than presenting real-life case studies or detailed examples of the practical application of the proposed tools and methods. Instead, the CYLCOMED architecture is a central example, offering an entry point to discuss the EU's cybersecurity legal frameworks and the challenges associated with these regulatory structures. The article also does not discuss the weaknesses of existing healthcare hardware devices or compare them with other technological solutions, as its focus is not strictly technical. In line with this course, the article is thereby divided into distinct sections. After a brief introduction, section 2 discusses academic interests in cyberattacks by investigating the security challenges brought about by an increasingly connected medical device and the highly dynamic environment in which it operates. Additionally, Section 2 provides precise terminology clarification to facilitate better navigation and understanding throughout this article. Section 3 stresses healthcare cybersecurity challenges by examining connected medical devices. Section 4 provides a brief overview of the CYLCOMED architecture and the main objectives and innovations of the CYLCOMED project, which aims to strengthen the cybersecurity of connected, in vitro diagnostics and software as medical devices. Focusing strongly on the CYLCOMED example, Section 5 analyses legal implications by stressing relevant EU legal sources to the cybersecurity of connected medical devices. The last section concludes.

The methodology in this article involves a thematic analysis of existing cybersecurity challenges within the healthcare sector, focusing on Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) and the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) following the CYLCOMED example. The article reviews critical aspects of the healthcare cybersecurity landscape by referencing recent incidents, challenges and regulatory frameworks. Additionally, the article outlines the structure and objectives of the CYLCOMED project, an EU-funded initiative aimed at addressing CMD cybersecurity. Through a structured examination of EU legal frameworks, including the GDPR, Medical Device Regulation (MDR), NIS2 Directive, and the AI Act, the article stresses the regulatory implications for CMDs' cybersecurity, providing a foundational understanding of how these regulations impact CMD management in healthcare.

2 A brief overview of academic interests in cybersecurity of medical devices

Over the past five years, there has been a substantial surge in academic interest in cybersecurity in the healthcare sector. A cursory analysis of the Scopus databases highlights this exponential growth, with a notable publication uptick. The analysis, which contained the keywords "Cybersecurity" AND "Health" in their abstracts, has shown that between 2017 and 2023, a total of 724 papers were published (Scopus). This was a clear contrast to the preceding period of 2003 to 2017, during which only 77 papers were published. This surge in research output highlights the increasing recognition of the critical intersection between cybersecurity and health in academic discourse.

Furthermore, the widely cited WannaCry ransomware attack in 2017 is just one of many examples that clearly illustrate the severe consequences of cyber threats in the healthcare sector (Wirth, 2017). WannaCry is one of the most intimidating ransomware attacks on health care to this date, which seriously hampered the National Health Service's (NHS) ability to provide patient care, causing the cancellation of nearly 7000 medical appointments, infection of critical medical equipment, and exposure of sensitive patient data, according to National Audit Office Report (2017). It spread to 200,000 machines across more than 100 countries (Walker-Roberts et al., 2018), inflicting a staggering £92 million loss on the NHS (Cyber Security Policy, 2018).

In addition to adverse events in 2017, cyberattacks on the IT infrastructure of hospitals, electronic health records, or medical devices during the COVID-19 pandemic have emphasised the critical need to ensure cybersecurity in the healthcare sector (Biasin et al., 2023a). This is clearly exemplified by the Conti ransomware attack on Ireland's Health Service Executive in 2021 (Pattnaik et al., 2023) and the most recent Change Healthcare ransomware cyberattack in 2024, which is labelled as "the most significant and consequential incident of its kind against the US health care system in history" (Pollack, 2024, p1).

2.1. Foundational Terms for Navigating Healthcare Cybersecurity

This subsection introduces essential terminology related to connected medical devices to facilitate comprehension of the complex landscape of cybersecurity in healthcare. This makes the article content accessible to a broad audience, including those less familiar with the intricacies of cybersecurity and healthcare technology.

2.1.2. Connected medical devices (CMDs)

Once only manufactured to be set up on hospital premises, contemporary medical devices can now generate, collect, analyse, transmit, and store substantial amounts of data while communicating with each other. While the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR) does not explicitly define the term connected medical devices (CMDs), for clarity in terminology within this paper, *connected medical devices are medical devices that are or incorporate software and artificial intelligence tools, utilising communication technologies, networks, and cloud services to transfer, manage, store, and analyse health data* (Mkwashi & Brass, 2022, p. 9).

2.1.3. Internet of Medical Things (IoMT)

The purpose of enhancing patient healthcare and improving service provision has led to increased integration and connectivity of medical devices into extensive IT systems. Devices like implantable ones (e.g., pacemakers and insulin pumps), wearables (e.g., blood pressure monitors and biosensors), and hospital-based medical equipment are now commonly connected to the Internet, forming what is often referred to as the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT). Notably, the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) refers to an interconnected ecosystem of medical devices and applications designed to collect, analyse, and transmit health-related data over the internet. Often seen as a healthcare-specific subset of the Internet of Things (IoT), IoMT enables the seamless transfer of patient information, supporting applications such as remote patient monitoring, diagnostic tools, and telemedicine services.

Therefore, the IoMT is an umbrella term encompassing all internet-connected medical devices utilising digital infrastructure for collecting, analysing, and processing health data. However, it is interesting to note that no single and widely adopted definition of IoT exists. It has different meanings to different people. It is sometimes referred to in EU legal acts such as the Data Act (Recital 14) and Cybersecurity Act (Recital 2). However, none of these defines its meaning. The same can be said for the IoMT.

While the Internet of Things (IoT) finds applications in various sectors (Srivastava and Pallavi, 2022), its impact on healthcare is particularly noteworthy, revolutionising the delivery of healthcare services. The IoMT facilitates real-time patient monitoring and behaviour modification, particularly in managing chronic conditions like diabetes and high blood pressure. Its applications in healthcare span from smart hospitals to remote health monitoring, disease diagnosis, and even tracking infectious diseases (Huang et al., 2023).

In the US, for example, there are approximately 10 to 15 internet-connected devices for each hospital bed, and many of these devices are susceptible to cyber-attacks (CISO Global, 2018). According to Anderson and Fagerberg (2023), the number of remotely

monitored patients reached 56.8 million in 2021. The estimation suggests a compound annual growth rate of 14.2 per cent, anticipating a rise to 126.1 million by 2027.

As connectivity in the healthcare sector has grown, offering benefits like real-time patient care and cost reduction, it has also introduced challenges. The increase in connected medical devices has expanded potential attack surfaces, making each device a potential entry point for cyber threats. With the exponential growth in the number of connected devices, the scale of potential attacks becomes overwhelming. In this complex environment, an attack on one device can compromise the entire system. Scholars, including Yaqoob, Abbas and Atiquzzaman (2019), have identified seven possible attack vectors within the communication structure of devices interacting with physicians, cloud-assisted data centres, hospital management systems, and data analytics systems. These vectors encompass vulnerabilities in Software/Firmware/Hardware, communication protocols like BLE/ZigBee/Wi-Fi/RF/Ethernet, personal computer or smartphone apps, and app connections to the gateway through Wi-Fi. Exploiting vulnerabilities at multiple entry points can lead to severe consequences.

Next, the foundational concept of the intended purpose plays a pivotal role in the EU regulatory framework outlined by the MDR. MDR Recital 19 offers concise elucidation, specifying instances where software should not be classified as a medical device. Notably, software designed for general or lifestyle purposes, even within healthcare contexts, falls outside the purview of medical devices. However, when a device explicitly articulates a medical purpose, it becomes subject to rigorous MDR requirements. This regulatory paradigm has encountered challenges in the contemporary surge of mobile health applications over the past decade. These applications often emulate functionalities associated with medical devices but, lacking an explicitly designated medical purpose, evade stringent MDR obligations. This exemption raises apprehensions about the adequacy of safety and security standards, particularly concerning user privacy.

The expansion of mobile health applications introduces complexities, making patient data processing less transparent than in conventional healthcare settings. In healthcare scenarios, the revolution of vital patient signs is clearly defined—gathered by sensors, transmitted through communication channels (such as Wi-Fi or Bluetooth) to centralised servers, processed, analysed, and subsequently shared with authorised physicians. Contrarily, in the realm of lifestyle and well-being mobile applications, this data processing becomes obscured, leading to uncertainties regarding data accessibility, potential third-party sharing practices, and the efficacy of safeguarding mechanisms. Unsurprisingly, it is often acknowledged that these apps do not meet even the basic GDPR requirements (Papageorgiou et al., 2018), lack essential privacy safeguards, and lack regulatory oversight (Quinn, 2017). Consequently, users of such applications become susceptible targets for cyberattacks.

2.1.4. AI and Cybersecurity

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) play an increasingly significant role in the cybersecurity of CMDs and IoMT networks. By analyzing patterns in data traffic and device behavior, AI and ML applications can detect and diagnose

security threats in real time, providing crucial layers of protection for healthcare systems. These intelligent systems enable the early identification of anomalies and potential threats, continuously adapting to evolving cyber risks, thereby providing essential support for healthcare providers managing connected device security. However, integrating artificial intelligence (AI) applications in healthcare further complicates the challenge of ensuring a secure cybersecurity environment. It is crucial to recognise that complete mitigation of cyber threats is impossible. As expressed by Weber and Studer (2016, p719), the question now is not whether but when a thing such as Medical Health Records (MHR) will be breached. Another underlying challenge is the blurring line between medical devices and mobile health applications (Rak, 2021).

2.1.5. The European Union Cybersecurity Legal Frameworks

Cybersecurity legal frameworks are structured guidelines and protocols developed to secure systems, networks, and data against cyber threats. Several key frameworks underpin the European Union (EU) regulatory landscape for cybersecurity in healthcare, such as the EU Cybersecurity Act, Medical Device Regulation, Network and Information System Directive, General Data Protection Regulation, and Artificial Intelligence Act.

3 The Overview Of Healthcare Cyber Threat Landscape

According to the EU Cybersecurity Act (2019), cybersecurity encompasses activities to safeguard network and information systems, their users, and others affected by cyber threats. Accordingly, cybersecurity is critical in protecting computer systems and networks from various threats. While delving into the healthcare cybersecurity landscape, it is essential to understand the motivations behind malicious attacks, the associated risks, and the vulnerabilities inherent in the sector.

Malicious cyberattacks can stem from diverse motivations, ranging from thrill-seeking and intellectual property theft to advancing political agendas (Piggin, 2017). Furthermore, in cybersecurity literature, financial gain is identified as a primary motivation driving attacks on healthcare infrastructure, given the wealth of sensitive data. Notably, health data holds significant value on the black market, surpassing data from other industries (MacIntyre et al., 2018). In short, Electronic Health Records (EHR) are desirable targets due to their comprehensive nature, encompassing personal information such as birth dates, social security numbers, credit card details, and extensive medical data, including history, diagnoses, medications, radiology images, laboratory results, and mental health conditions. Stolen personal health information can bring substantial sums, ranging from \$10 to \$1,000 per record, depending on its completeness (Humer & Finkle, 2014; Stack, 2017). Unauthorised access to such data facilitates additional fraudulent activities, such as submitting false insurance claims (Javaid et al., 2023). Beyond financial motives, ideological reasons and espionage also serve as driving forces for cybercriminals.

A successful cyberattack carries substantial implications with extreme effects on both hospitals and patients. Primarily, security breaches impose additional costs on the healthcare sector, which already operates under financial constraints (Perakslis, 2014). According to the ENISA NIS Investments Report (2022), a significant security incident in the health sector has a median cost of 300,000 euros. Besides ENISA, IBM's Cost of a Data Breach Report (2023) identified healthcare breach costs as the highest among industries for 13 consecutive years, increasing by 53.3% since the 2020 report. Hospitals may incur high financial costs due to patient compensation and regulatory fines (Silver et al., 2016). For instance, the Finnish psychotherapy centre Vastaamo faced a fine of EUR 608,000 for GDPR violations related to securing personal data and reporting a data breach (EDPB 2022).

Beyond financial repercussions, the disruption of healthcare services is among the most severe consequences of malicious attacks. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, Brno University Hospital in the Czech Republic experienced a ransomware attack, leading to an immediate computer shutdown and the postponement of surgeries (Porter, 2020). Similarly, a ransomware attack on a German hospital disrupted emergency services, resulting in a patient's death. While German law enforcement authorities determined that the attack was not directly responsible for the patient's death, such scenarios emphasise the potential for serious harm (Howell, 2020). Examples of these incidents significantly damage healthcare reputations, erode credibility, and undermine patient trust (Shenoy and Appel, 2017). On a different note, exposing sensitive health data may have harmful effects on patients' well-being, ranging from negative community perceptions to embarrassment, stigmatisation, and even loss of career opportunities (Waegemann, 1996).

Alongside violating patient privacy, malicious attacks can lead to physical harm and life-threatening situations. For example, wireless medical devices like insulin pumps and pacemakers can be hacked (Takahashi, 2011). Radiofrequency (RF) signals sent to an insulin pump can alter settings and impact insulin dosage, posing potentially fatal outcomes (Levy-Loboda et al., 2022). Due to cybersecurity vulnerabilities in specific insulin pumps, the medical device company Medtronic issued an urgent recall and recommended that patients change to a newer model with enhanced cybersecurity protection (Medtronic, 2019).

In achieving all the above-mentioned cyber-attacks, perpetrators employ various malicious techniques, such as ransomware, distributed denial of service (DDoS), hijacking, remote code execution, and social engineering, to achieve their aims. According to ENISA (2023a), ransomware remains the most deployed attack in the health sector in 2023, with an increase in both the EU and globally. ENISA, in the Threat Landscape for Ransomware Attacks Report (2022), defines ransomware as an attack where threat actors take control of a target's assets and demand a ransom in exchange for the return of the assets' availability. Additionally, ENISA (2023b) highlighted the rise of DoS attacks (attacks against availability) in 2023, which are identified as one of the top threats with an upward trend.

3.1 HealthCare cybersecurity challenges

The healthcare industry is susceptible to cyberattacks and lags behind other sectors for various reasons. While this article does not delve deeply into these issues, it is crucial to briefly highlight the most pressing ones. Primarily, providing healthcare services has traditionally been oriented towards patient care without considering cybersecurity risks. With the continual evolution of cyber threats, healthcare professionals face additional challenges within an already demanding environment. Notably, the human factor is identified as the most critical element in fortifying cybersecurity in healthcare. Many information security incidents stem from human error, which is consistently acknowledged as the weakest link in the cybersecurity chain (Evans et al., 2019).

The lack of cybersecurity training and awareness among healthcare professionals, combined with a stressful environment, renders them susceptible to attacks rooted in social engineering, such as (spear)phishing and whaling (Al-Qahtani and Cresci, 2022). Besides, the shortage of cybersecurity professionals is well-acknowledged worldwide (ENISA, 2020; NIST, 2020) and represents one of the biggest challenges in the future (ENISA, 2023c). For example, according to the ISC2 (2023) Cybersecurity Workforce Study, the global cybersecurity workforce gap has increased by 26.2% compared to 2021, with 3.4 million more workers needed to secure assets effectively.

The abovementioned challenge is particularly evident in the healthcare sector (Kotz et al., 2016). This is exacerbated by the fact that a medical device cybersecurity expert requires different skill sets than a traditional IT security engineer or architect (Ray Arnab, 2021). The Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society's "Healthcare Cybersecurity Survey" (2022) reveals that limited budgets and financial constraints further hinder hospitals' ability to attract and retain cybersecurity professionals. Other underlying vulnerabilities are mirrored in the lack of awareness of cybersecurity issues, training on cybersecurity risks and poor security practices such as password sharing (Williams and Woodward, 2015). For example, instances of finding passwords written on notes attached to terminals, sharing access cards, and leaving systems unattended are not uncommon (Yigzaw et al., 2022).

The use of legacy devices is another reason behind the weak cybersecurity posture of healthcare institutions. Medical Device Regulators Forum IMDRF (2023, p8) defines legacy medical devices in the context of cybersecurity as "medical devices that cannot be reasonably protected against current cybersecurity threats". Legacy medical devices in current use were designed and manufactured long before the emergence of cybersecurity threats, therefore, without cybersecurity features in mind. Since medical devices have a long lifespan, many such devices still operate today, using outdated or insecure software, hardware and protocols. For instance, Windows XP is still present in a significant number of today's devices, an operating system with well-known security issues, years after Microsoft formally stopped providing cybersecurity support for it. More worryingly, some hospital equipment is still running on Windows 98, despite Microsoft stopping all support for the operating system in 2006 (Slabodkin, 2021). Legacy medical devices have not been manufactured to be connected to the Internet and to communicate with each other, let alone be cyber secure. However, due to financial constraints, the alteration of legacy medical devices with features that facilitate their

communication or internet connection is much cheaper than buying new medical equipment. However, these changes to legacy devices are limited since they lack the computational power to perform cryptographic operations without compromising basic functionality and available memory space to accommodate cryptographic software libraries, which makes them a soft target for cybercriminals. Consequently, connecting numerous medical devices and integrating them into large network systems presents a significant challenge, warranting particular attention in the following subsection.

4 CYLCOMED for cybersecurity of connected medical devices

As cyber-attacks are becoming more intense and sophisticated, the development of robust defensive strategies becomes imperative. A proactive cybersecurity culture is essential, and within this context, the CYLCOMED initiative seeks to fortify the cybersecurity of connected medical devices. The overarching goal is to address the security challenges delineated in this article and elevate cybersecurity standards within healthcare contexts. A primary focus of CYLCOMED lies in enhancing the safety and privacy facets of Connected Medical Devices. The CYLCOMED development of a cybersecurity toolbox follows this objective in supporting comprehensive defence strategies, the architecture of which is provided in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Current CYLCOMED's Toolbox Architecture

The CYLCOMED toolbox encompasses various tools designed to fortify the cybersecurity of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs). To better describe the structure of CYLCOMED's Toolbox, which showcases modularity, flexibility, adaptability, and

efficiency, the tools are organised into four layers forming the final toolbox architecture, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Data Collection and Analysis Layer collects, monitors, and analyses data from diverse sources within the CYLCOMED ecosystem to detect potential cybersecurity threats or anomalies proactively. It integrates two core components: the CMD Log Monitoring system and the behavioural analysis tool. These tools leverage artificial intelligence to examine logs and network traffic generated by connected medical devices and the platforms managing them. The aim is to identify unusual patterns or activities that could indicate a potential security incident. The primary function of this layer is to provide real-time, continuous surveillance of system activities, ensuring the prompt detection and response to emerging threats. It aggregates and processes large volumes of data from various sources, including network traffic, device logs, and other relevant streams, applying sophisticated algorithms to detect deviations from normal behaviour. This approach enables the system to recognise even subtle signs of potential compromise. By constantly monitoring and analysing these signs, this layer plays a vital role in enhancing the security posture of the CYLCOMED ecosystem, helping to safeguard the integrity and reliability of the connected medical infrastructure. For instance, while AI-based CMD Behavioral Analysis utilises machine learning algorithms to scrutinise data transmission patterns from CMDs and identify abnormalities indicative of security breaches, AI-powered Log Monitoring aims to automatically detect anomalies in system/application logs, thus improving performance and ensuring security.

Device Integrity, Security and Service Management Layer's primary objective is to uphold the operational integrity of medical devices, safeguarding them against unauthorised modifications and ensuring their lifecycle management remains secure. This layer includes mechanisms facilitating secure firmware updates and configurations aligned with healthcare standards and regulations. These protections not only prevent tampering but also ensure that updates and configurations meet strict regulatory requirements, thereby enhancing device reliability and patient safety throughout the device's lifecycle. Tools integrated into this layer serve two main functions. First, they enable connected medical devices' security maintenance by establishing a secure management infrastructure for device updates and configurations, ultimately minimising the attack surface. Second, they provide connected medical device integrity checks, focusing on preserving security features and ensuring the integrity of the devices without compromising their regulatory certification.

Hence, the tools integrated into this layer prioritise essential functionalities to optimise service delivery, strengthen security, and improve operational efficiency, specifically:

- Ensure secure updates of services on medical devices.
- Reduce the attack surface for both medical devices and cloud infrastructure.
- Detect misconfigurations promptly.
- Maintain code integrity and configuration integrity across all connected medical devices.

The identity, Access Management, and Data Protection Layer establishes strong access control and data protection mechanisms tailored to healthcare's unique requirements. This layer enforces encryption and secure data-sharing protocols, acting as the system's gatekeeper by managing access through predefined policies and user roles to uphold data privacy and comply with legal and ethical standards.

Built on a decentralised self-sovereign identity framework, this layer prioritises patient privacy and the confidentiality of sensitive data produced by CMDs, ensuring that unauthorised data access is effectively prevented. Additionally, CYLCOMED's data protection approach, centred on encrypting CMD-generated data, aligns with regulatory requirements, such as the General Data Protection Regulation, and secures data both in transit and at rest, thereby reducing cybersecurity risks. For instance, this layer's Decentralized Identity Management and Data Protection tools enhance identity management and data security through a decentralised approach, enabling privacy-preserving, secure data exchange between devices and healthcare providers. This is achieved using advanced encryption methods, such as Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption (CP-ABE), which facilitates secure, controlled access to data while maintaining patient privacy and confidentiality.

The Security Dashboard and Visualization Layer is the topmost layer of the CYLCOMED architecture. The **Security Dashboard** provides a comprehensive view of the system's cybersecurity state by centralizing the reporting and visualization of security alerts, anomalies, and metrics. Serving as a centralised Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) tool, its primary function is to aggregate, analyse, and display security data from across the CYLCOMED framework, delivering real-time situational awareness for cybersecurity events and enabling timely and effective incident response.

This dashboard synthesises data from various sources, including the AI Behavioural Analysis component, network traffic monitoring, and vulnerability assessments, to produce a continuous and accurate representation of the security status of connected medical devices. Its key responsibilities within the CYLCOMED framework are:

- Real-time monitoring of connected medical devices,
- Alert generation and incident notification,
- Vulnerability assessment and management to proactively address security risks and
- Comprehensive reporting and analysis to support evidence-based security decision-making.

This layer is integral to sustaining the integrity and security of the CYLCOMED ecosystem, providing the analytical depth required for a resilient cybersecurity posture.

Collectively, these tools contribute to CYLCOMED's mission of enhancing cybersecurity standards and mitigating potential threats in the realm of Connected Medical Devices. The performance and applicability of the CYLCOMED technical solutions will be demonstrated by implementing the developed tools in two dedicated pilots.

Pilot 1 (Figure 2), Cybersecurity in Hospital Equipment for COVID-19 ICU Patients, will be carried out as a digital twin simulation without direct human participation. This pilot focuses on a muscular relaxation infusion controller, a medical device vital for

COVID-19 ICU patients. The controller measures the patient's relaxometry levels, adjusting infusion doses accordingly. The infusion pump is regulated, and alarms manage relaxation levels automatically. The pilot, conducted in a controlled laboratory environment, is a proof of concept with no involvement of actual patients. Critical aspects of Pilot 1 include:

- **Test Scenario:** A prototypical implementation of the testbench and an autonomous intelligent controller assesses the functionality and performance of the muscular relaxation infusion controller.
- **Objective:** To test the connected medical device integrity solution and address the medical equipment needs in an "on-premises" scenario.
- **Interaction with CYLCOMED:** The CMD interacts with CYLCOMED through a single-board computer, emphasising the connected medical device integrity solution as the core, complemented by other tools offering their benefits.

This pilot aims to demonstrate the practicality and effectiveness of CYLCOMED's technical solutions in a simulated healthcare environment.

Fig. 2. Pilot 1 Architecture

Pilot 2 (Figure 3), Cybersecurity for Telemedicine Platforms, will be conducted as an observational study, including patient participation. This pilot addresses critical vulnerabilities associated with connected medical devices (CMDs) and their gateways, focusing on ensuring the integrity of patient data transmitted to telemedicine platforms. As telemedicine's role expands in healthcare, protecting against data breaches, tampering, and misuse of medical devices becomes increasingly crucial. Notably, the pilot uniquely emphasises real-world applications and integration. Critical aspects of the pilot include:

- **Objective:** Ensuring the integrity of patient data transmitted to telemedicine platforms, safeguarding against data breaches and misuse of medical devices.
- **Significance:** With a growing reliance on telemedicine, this pilot addresses key cybersecurity concerns in healthcare, offering a comprehensive evaluation of the CYLCOMED toolbox.
- **Strategic Approach:** Simulated testing allows the assessment of sensitive components, ensuring the toolbox's reliability and effectiveness in both real and simulated scenarios.
- **Innovation and Adaptability:** By bringing developed tools into real-world applications, CYLCOMED demonstrates its commitment to innovation and adaptability in the evolving landscape of telemedicine cybersecurity.

The pilot involves enhancing the Mediaclinics Health Platform, focusing on paediatric patients. Clinicians will utilise the platform's remote monitoring capabilities to record and evaluate vital parameters from young patients. This approach strengthens cybersecurity and sets a precedent for secure and efficient telemedicine practices in healthcare.

Fig. 3. MHP Architecture

5 Exploring Legal Implications and EU Regulations for Connected Medical Devices

Regulating cybersecurity, especially in the context of medical devices, is a complex challenge due to the specialised and fragmented nature of the legal framework (Chowdhury and Wessel, 2012). The complexity of cybersecurity technology, such as the proposed CYLCOMED technology, arises from the intersection of various EU legislative

frameworks and their potential applicability. Consequently, this complexity is compounded by the need to navigate both medical device regulations and cybersecurity laws (Biasin and Kamenjasevic, 2020). When it comes to the legal requirements for the cybersecurity of medical devices, the EU laws establish a set of different requirements enshrined in the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR), In vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices (IVDR), the Cybersecurity Act (CSA), the Network and Information Systems Directive (NIS2), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Radio Equipment Directive (RED) and recently adopted Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act). The following subsections will provide a brief examination of these relevant legal frameworks.

5.1 Medical Device Regulation (MDR)

The MDR is the most crucial piece of legislation applicable to the cybersecurity of medical devices. The introduction of the MDR has emerged as a response to the risks and challenges posed by technological advancements in healthcare. In contrast to the previously repealed Medical Device Directive, the MDR imposes more rigorous requirements for bringing medical devices to the EU market or putting them into service inside of the EU. To ensure a high level of safety and performance of medical devices incorporating electronic programmable systems and software that is a medical device in itself, MDR requires a demonstration of compliance with the cybersecurity rules that are encompassed by the General and Safety Performance Requirements enlisted in Annex I (Article 5(2)).

According to Article 2(1) MDR, a medical device is defined as any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material, or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more specific medical purposes. These purposes include diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment, alleviation of disease, investigation, replacement, or modification of anatomy or physiological/pathological processes or states. For instance, under the scope of the definition falls everything from plaster, disposable gloves to pacemakers and radiation systems (Malvey et al., 2022).

To assist device manufacturers in adhering to the essential requirements in Annex I of the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) concerning cybersecurity, the European Commission's Medical Device Coordination Group endorsed the Guidance on Cybersecurity for Medical Devices MDCG 2019-16 Rev.1 (MDCG Guidance). Being the first guidance on medical device cybersecurity, it marked a significant advancement in facilitating the implementation of MDR cybersecurity provisions. However, the medical device cybersecurity landscape is a dynamic field that has undergone significant changes since the MDCG Guidance endorsement in 2019. Scholars, including Biasin and Kamenjasevic (2020), have astutely identified areas for improvement in the MDCG Guidance. These include clarifying concepts such as joint responsibility and improving terminological coherence. These refinements are essential for the benefit of all stakeholders involved in medical device cybersecurity. The practical implementation of cybersecurity requirements outlined in the MDR has become more complex due to recent changes in the EU's regulatory frameworks that intersect with the medical device

cybersecurity domain. Notably, introducing regulations like NIS2 has added an additional layer of intricacy to navigating and adhering to MDR cybersecurity provisions.

5.2 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The GDPR is particularly relevant to the cybersecurity of medical devices because these devices involve processing significant amounts of personal data, including sensitive data. The GDPR establishes rules for safeguarding individuals in processing their personal and sensitive data, specifically focusing on health-related data. As outlined in GDPR Article 25, one of the central requirements is the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures and necessary safeguards to ensure the practical application of data protection principles by design and default.

According to GDPR Article 25(1), data controllers and/or processors are mandated to establish appropriate technical and organisational measures proportional to the data processing risk. State-of-the-art criteria must be considered when implementing these measures. However, the term state-of-the-art is not precisely defined in the GDPR. In its Recital 78, the GDPR provides some examples of technical and organisational measures. However, the specific meaning of state-of-the-art remains open and subject to ongoing technological advancements, as the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) acknowledges in its Guidelines on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default. While the GDPR obliges the data controllers and/or processors to ground the implementation of these measures on the risk-based approach, considering the current technological progress, the practical implementation leaves room for different interpretations of what constitutes the state-of-the-art.

5.3 Network and Information Systems Directive (NISD)

The Network and Information Security Directive (NISD) 2016/1148/EU is considered to be the first piece of EU-wide cybersecurity legislation, which aimed, among other things, to build cybersecurity capabilities across the Union and mitigate threats to network and information systems (Markopoulou et al., 2019). Despite its significant achievements, such as a positive shift in the cybersecurity framework and improved cyber resilience of public and private entities, the European Commission's Impact assessment (2020) on the NIS Directive has demonstrated its limitations over time. Due to identified shortcomings in implementing the NIS Directive, it was repealed by the NIS2 Directive, which introduced various novelties and expanded the scope of its application. While the repealed Directive has encompassed the healthcare sector, the NIS2 expands its scope of application to new entities. It applies to manufacturers of medical devices, imposing additional cybersecurity requirements established in the NIS2 Directive on these entities.

NIS2 differentiates two categories of entities that fall within the scope of the Directive: essential entities and important entities listed in Annexes I and II of the NIS 2 Directive. The distinction between them is based on the criticality of essential entities and important entities concerning their sector or the type of service they provide, their size, and a compliance obligation. These will be subject to cybersecurity risk

management and reporting obligations, and they will be supervised, to different degrees, by the competent authorities. With reporting obligation, it has been acknowledged that certain malicious attacks can invoke the simultaneous application of MDR's and NIS2's provisions, thus causing legal uncertainty and overlap (Biasin and Kamenjasevic, 2020). However, the specific requirements mandated by the NIS2 are still ambiguous, as the detailed requirements of the NIS2 Directive are to be released by October 2024. More specifically, Member States shall adopt and publish the measures necessary to comply with this Directive by 17 October 2024 (Article 41).

5.4 Cyber Security Act (CSA)

The Cyber Security Act (CSA) aims to ensure the proper functioning of the EU's internal market by reaching a high level of cybersecurity of network and information systems, communication networks, services, and devices within the Union. CSA establishes the first EU-wide cybersecurity certification framework to ensure a common cybersecurity certification approach in the European internal market and ultimately improve cybersecurity in a broad range of digital products and services. Certification is seen as vital for increasing the trust and security of ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes (CSA Recital 69). Besides, cybersecurity certification aims to overcome the fragmentation and overlapping of national cybersecurity certification schemes. Furthermore, it strives to enable a harmonised approach at the Union level to European cybersecurity certification schemes to create a single digital market for ICT products, ICT services, and ICT processes. However, it is essential to note that according to the CSA Article 56(2), cybersecurity certification is voluntary unless otherwise specified by EU or Member State regulations. If some member states were to require a mandatory cybersecurity certification, it would mean that manufacturers would have to obtain a cybersecurity certificate for a device to be marketed within a particular Member State. However, this requirement may not be necessary in other Member States, causing inconsistency across countries (Biasin and Kamenjasevic, 2020). In such cases, manufacturers of devices that obtained CE marking might be obliged to undergo an additional certification process, thus causing duplication of requirements and additional costs. Additionally, the recently adopted AI Act introduces a certification mechanism, which will add an additional layer of complexity to this domain.

5.5 Radio Equipment Directive (RED)

The Radio Equipment Directive (RED) establishes a regulatory framework for making available on the EU market and putting radio equipment into service. Certain types of medical devices (such as pacemakers or implantable cardioverter defibrillators) are likely to fall under the scope of the Directive and thus be subject to its security requirements. All internet-connected radio equipment that is Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, LTE, 5G, or GPS enabled falls under the scope of RED. Consequently, the RED applies to medical devices if they include components such as Wi-Fi or Bluetooth modules, which means that, apart from meeting stringent MDR requirements, medical device manufacturers

will need to comply with RED, conduct conformity assessment under its rules, and declare conformity with RED, in addition to the MDR. Additionally, the Commission adopted a Delegated Act of the Radio Equipment Directive, which aims to increase the level of cybersecurity, personal data protection and privacy for specific categories of radio equipment. The Delegated Regulation has brought clarity and relief to medical device manufacturers as it excludes medical devices from its scope regarding cybersecurity requirements (Article 2(1a)).

5.6 AI Act

The AI Act, a landmark piece of legislation regulating artificial intelligence technologies, was published in the European Journal on July 12, 2024. Its primary goal is to mitigate risks to health, safety, and fundamental rights associated with AI technologies. This comprehensive legislation, with its broad scope of application, including the medical device sector, is set to significantly impact the industry.

However, it is worth noting that AI is not a novelty in healthcare settings. Artificial intelligence has made significant inroads into the medical field, enhancing diagnostic accuracy, personalising treatment plans, and improving patient outcomes. In the medical devices domain, AI-driven technologies have been deployed for advanced imaging, predictive analytics, and even robotic surgeries. AI medical devices are subject to stringent requirements laid down by MDR. Moreover, many AI medical devices have been CE-marked under the now-repealed Medical Device Directive (Choi et al., 2022). However, some scholars have raised serious concerns that due to the unique nature of AI, MDR falls short of regulating these unique characteristics (Li et al., 2023; Mkwashi & Brass, 2022).

Upon enforcing the AI Act, medical device manufacturers will be required to comply with additional obligations stipulated by the AI Act, in conjunction with the existing MDR requirements, which will undoubtedly add another layer of complexity to the already complex regulatory landscape. Namely, most AI medical device software will fall under the scope of high-risk AI systems (Article 6(1)) since all medical device software class IIa and higher needs to undergo a third-party conformity assessment. Some of the new requirements refer to data and data governance (Article 10), Record-keeping (Article 12) and Human oversight (Article 14), to mention just a few. Consequently, medical device manufacturers, apart from MDR requirements, will have to comply with requirements for high-risk AI systems established by the AI Act, which will undoubtedly significantly affect the MedTech industry, raising overall compliance costs. Many scholars have already highlighted potential duplication and inconsistency in the interplay between the MDR and the AI Act (Choi et al., 2022; Biasin et al., 2023b). Moreover, all applicable requirements are outlined at a high level, lacking detailed specifications for their implementation. To avoid legal uncertainty, it is crucial to clarify the relationship between the MDR and the AI Act and the practical implementation of high-level requirements. In this regard, industrial standards and MDCG guidance are expected to play crucial roles in facilitating compliance. Although the European Commission has issued a standardisation request to the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation

(CENELEC) to support safe and trustworthy artificial intelligence, the timeline for developing these standards remains uncertain due to the lengthy and complex nature of the process.

While the AI Act addresses cybersecurity through several recitals and articles, it is not cybersecurity legislation per se. Its Recital 76 AI Act acknowledges that cybersecurity is fundamental in safeguarding AI systems against attempts by malicious entities to alter their utilisation, behaviour, and performance or to compromise their security attributes by exploiting system vulnerabilities. AI cybersecurity is encompassed within Article 15 of the AI Act, although not as an individual requirement, but integrated with considerations of accuracy and robustness. AI Act Article 15(1) prescribes that high-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way that they achieve an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity and that they perform consistently in those respects throughout their lifecycle. However, their practical implementation is still ambiguous since the cybersecurity requirements are outlined in broad terms. Additionally, despite provisions addressing cybersecurity, some scholars (Biasin et al., 2023b) have noted that the AI Act does not explicitly reference the Cybersecurity Act's definition of cybersecurity. This omission is significant, as it would establish a stronger connection to individual cybersecurity protection.

6 CONCLUSION

The health sector faces persistent threats, with patient data, including electronic health records, ranking as the primary target. Despite increased attention and policy efforts, the healthcare industry lags in terms of cybersecurity maturity and competence compared to sectors like industrial and financial.

This article emphasises the critical importance of cybersecurity in healthcare, particularly for CMDs and the IoMT. With healthcare's increasing digitisation, CMDs are exposed to various cyber threats that can compromise patient safety, data privacy, and operational integrity.

Additionally, this article delves into the background of the proposed CYLCOMED cybersecurity solution situated within an interdisciplinary research paradigm. It further aims to analyse the leading cybersecurity challenges in the healthcare sector and introduce the ambitious goal of CYLCOMED cybersecurity solutions, which aims to strengthen the cybersecurity of connected medical devices. Following CYLCOMED as an example, the article explores the regulatory landscape, examining how EU legal frameworks set standards for cybersecurity in medical devices. The legal landscape surrounding cybersecurity in the EU is complex, involving various frameworks such as the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Network and Information Systems Directive (NISD), Cyber Security Act (CSA), Radio Equipment Directive (RED) and recently adopted AI Act.

Navigating these legal frameworks presents challenges, with recent changes such as NIS2 and AI Act adding complexity to the practical implementation of MDR cybersecurity requirements. The GDPR is particularly relevant due to the vast amount of

personal data processed by medical devices, emphasising the need for appropriate technical and organisational measures.

Although the CYLCOMED project's architecture aligns with these regulations, the evolving legal landscape and the dynamic nature of medical devices and cybersecurity necessitate ongoing adaptation. Challenges persist, such as clarifying joint responsibility and improving terminological coherence, to mention just a few.

In conclusion, CYLCOMED's proactive approach, incorporating a robust cybersecurity toolbox and real-world pilot implementations, aligns with the imperative to address the evolving challenges in connected medical device cybersecurity. Ongoing legal developments add layers of complexity, emphasising the need for continuous adaptation and collaboration across stakeholders in the healthcare and cybersecurity domains.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Dusko Milojevic and Maja Nisevic declare not to have any conflict of interest.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in this article.

Acknowledgement

CYLCOMED [Cyber securitY tooLbox for COnnected MEdical Devices] project has received funding from the European Union's (Horizon Europe) research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101095542.

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